

Human Capital Management in a Time Bound Public Sector Developmental Project: A Case Study of the National Rural Health Mission

Dr. Krishna Kant Sharma¹

Abstract— Projectification of companies has truly become a global phenomenon now; in fact, several companies world over have transformed themselves into a project based organizations to improve performance. When enterprises move towards projectification several HR actions seem affected? Government of India to achieve its public health objectives has adopted a project based approach whereby putting in place several structural changes under the aegis of National Health Mission (NHM) and its two submissions, namely National Rural Health Mission (NRHM) and National Urban Health Mission (NUHM).

This paper is based upon a research project sponsored by the University Grants Commission (UGC) under which case studies and employee survey were organized. Various functional layers of human resources management were studied with the help of specially designed tools.

There was a lack of HR professionals in the public health sector and most of HR functions were implemented by the government and medical staff who were not trained in managing HR affairs. Several new structures were embedded in a permanent structure of the department of health. Most of such new organizations were in the form of healthy societies. Employees were recruited on contract basis through the new organizations and there was tension between the permanent and contract staff. There was not proper attention on employee performance and performance based rewarding, the level of job satisfaction was one of the lowest and there was substantial outward migration of the workforce. The lack of talent and knowledge management was one of the reasons why the public health sector underperformed. There was not any dedicated digital file of the employees and it was difficult to access who did what and how? The public health sector was suffering with a crisis of workforce, especially doctors and paramedics.

Key words: Projectified Government Organization; Public Health Sector in India: Human Capital Management.

1. Introduction:

The National Health Mission (NHM) was a major intervention of the government of India intended to fortify the public health system of the country. One of its components, namely the *National Rural Health Mission* (NRHM) was launched in April 2005 whereas its second component National Urban Health Mission (NUHM) started in 2014. ^[1]

One of the strategic concepts in the contemporary Human Resources Management (HRM) was that HRM must be closely associated with the objective of the concern and it should be placed in proximity with the core decision making body. There has been a marked divergence between HR practices in the public sector and private sector ^[2]. In India after first economic liberalization in 1991 several innovative HR policies came into practice which promoted the performance of the companies mostly in private sector ^[3]. Such innovations were also adopted by certain government departments in order to achieve the desired objectives. The required objectives for the public health sector in the country forced the government to transform themselves or create new administrative arrangements to function as a project based organization. Certain HR considerations were easy to perform in a project based organization rather than in a governmental set up, which mostly regulated by certain rigid principles, guidelines or norms. Therefore, HR considerations could have compelled a government structure to create or function as a Project Based Organization. There may be other reasons also for this transformation, but they didn't include in this study. It was reported that

some HR considerations were among various other reasons that may have pushed towards such transformation of a government department going for a mission oriented or project based approach. Certain HR measures were essential in order to attain those public health objectives with which the Ministry of health and family welfare, Government of India was charged with. It was perhaps not possible to practice such HR actions in a government set up and certain transformations in administrative mechanism were required.

2. Aims and objectives:

The main aim and objectives of this study was to evaluate and assess the HR action under NRHM. Further the aim was also to explore the challenges and characteristics of HRM in project-based time bound organizations. The other objectives may be described as:

To examine the manner new arrangements were compatible with the agenda or mandate of the public health in India amidst international development and globalization.

To examine the HR policy and the manner they benefitted the public health attainments.

To explore the HR challenges in a project based organizations.

3. Literature review:

"NRHM Mission Documents" Ministry of health and family welfare, Government of India ^[1]: This was one of the most

¹ Head, Department of Labour and Social Welfare, KPS College, Nadwan, Patna-804453, Bihar. Email: kksharma69@yahoo.com; M: 9504782781.

vital document on NRHM which contained every sphere of NRHM such as its objectives, strategies, rationale, targets and mode of implementation. It stated that the National Rural Health Mission was launched by the Hon'ble Prime Minister on 12th April 2005, to provide accessible, affordable and accountable quality health services even to the poorest households in the remotest rural regions. The difficult areas with unsatisfactory health indicators were classified as special focus States to ensure greater attention where needed. The thrust of the Mission was on establishing a fully functional, community owned, decentralized health delivery system with inter sectoral convergence at all levels, to ensure simultaneous action on a wide range of determinants of health like water, sanitation, education, nutrition, social and gender equality. Institutional integration within the fragmented health sector was expected to provide a focus on outcomes, measured against Indian Public Health Standards for all health facilities. From narrowly defined schemes, the NRHM was shifting the focus to a functional health system at all levels, from the village to the district.

NRHM Framework of Implementation 2005-12, Ministry of health and family welfare, Government of India ^[4]: This was a 215 page document on NRHM which was released at the onset of NRHM in the year 2005 by the Ministry of health and family welfare, government of India. It contained every information on each subject of different issues related to implementation of NRHM. It suggested action points and prescribed a timeline to accomplish those action points. It described the goals, strategies and expected outcome of the mission. It prioritizes critical areas of concern under NRHM. It provided guidelines to institutional set up their memberships and merger of societies which was an important action point. Provisions for human resources, financial and data management, review and evaluation mechanism were also spelled out in details. Formats for byelaws and memorandum of healthy societies, Kalyan samitis, facility survey was also provided.

Strategies for Health Sector Reform in South and Southeast Asia ^[6]: This PowerPoint presentation provided information about Health Sector Reforms in India in the purview of National Rural Health Mission, National Urban Health Mission, Task force on accreditation, training and integration of Private Rural Medical Practitioners, Health System Reform and Ethics, Private Practitioners in Poor Urban Neighborhoods in India, Indonesia and Thailand.

Job satisfaction and motivation of health workers in public and private sectors: cross-sectional analysis of two Indian states ^[6]: This article said that there was high variability in the ratings for areas of satisfaction and motivation across the different practice settings, but there were also commonalities. Four groups of factors were identified, with those relating to job content and work environment viewed as the most important characteristics of the ideal job, and rated higher than a good income. In both states, public sector health workers rated "good employment benefits" as significantly more important than private sector workers, as well as a "superior who recognizes work". There were large differences in whether these factors were considered present on the job, particularly between public and private sector health workers in Uttar Pradesh, where the public sector fared

consistently lower ($P < 0.01$). The discordance between what motivational factors, health workers considered important and their perceptions of the actual presence of these factors were also highest in Uttar Pradesh in the public sector, where all 17 items had a greater discordance for public sector workers than for workers in the private sector.

Reviewing the Benefits of Health Workforce Stability ^[7]: This paper examines the issue of workforce stability and turnover in the context of policy attempts to improve retention of health workers. The paper argues that there are significant benefits to supporting policy makers and managers to develop a broader perspective of workforce stability and methods of monitoring it. The objective of the paper is to contribute to developing a better understanding of workforce stability as a major aspect of the overall policy goal of improved retention of health workers. The paper examines some of the limited research on the complex interaction between staff turnover and organizational performance or quality of care in the health sector, provides details and examples of the measurement of staff turnover and stability, and illustrates an approach to costing staff turnover. The paper concludes by advocating that these types of assessment can be valuable to managers and policy makers as they examine which policies may be effective in improving stability and retention, by reducing turnover. They can also be used as part of advocacy for the use of new retention measures. The very action of setting up a local working group to assess the costs of turnover can in itself give managers and staff a greater insight into the negative impacts of turnover, and can encourage them to work together to identify and implement stability measures.

Human resources for public health service by R. Kumar ^[8]: This article said that Human societies around the world are striving hard to improve the quality of life of their people. United Nations have given expression to this aspiration by setting up a number of the Millennium Development Goals covering the economic, social, and health dimensions. It is now well recognized that health development is one of the important prerequisites to realize basic human rights. Therefore, public policies that improve population health should receive due priority. Systematic efforts are required not only for assessment of the health needs of communities and populations, but also to plan, organize, and monitor health services so that these needs are met. To view of the scarce resources, most cost-effective and sustainable strategies need to be put in place. Therefore, there is a need to evolve and implement a human resource policy to strengthen public health service in India.

Human Resource Management in Project-Based Organizations - Challenges, Changes, and Capabilities by Karin Bredin ^[9]: This doctoral thesis addresses human resource management in project-based organizations. The aim is to explore the challenges for HRM in project-based organizations and the changes in people management systems to meet these challenges. The thesis consists of a compilation of six papers and an extended summary. The research reported in the thesis is based on a combination of multiple-, comparative, and single-case studies of project-based organizations. The core case studies have been conducted at Saab Aero systems, AstraZeneca, Volvo Car Corporation, and Tetra Pak. The results indicate central challenges re-

garding competence development and career structures, performance-review processes and reputation of project workers, and the increased responsibility and pressured work environment for project workers. They further indicate that many of these challenges are handled through a more HR-oriented line manager role, while HR departments are downsized and centralized. The thesis, hence emphasizes the need to understand HRM as an area of management in which various players share the responsibility for its design and performance. To conclude, the thesis applies a capabilities perspective on project-based organizations and develops a conceptual framework that embraces person's capability: the organizational capability to manage the relationship between people and their organizational context. In this framework, people management systems improve people capability when they integrate it with strategic, functional, and project capabilities. It is suggested that the people capability framework provides new possibilities to analyze HRM in project-based organizations and to explain the changes in people management systems that are needed to align them to the project-based context.

HUMAN RESOURCES FOR PUBLIC HEALTH IN INDIA – ISSUES AND CHALLENGES by **Deoki Nandan, K.S. Nair and U. Datta** ^[10]: This article told about the availability of adequate number of human resources with suitable skill mix and their appropriate deployment at different levels of health care set-up are essential for providing effective health care services for the population. Since independence, concerted efforts have been made to address the need for human resources for health in India. However, the shortage exists in all categories of human resources at different levels. Ensuring the availability of human resources for health in rural areas and building their capacity in public health are daunting tasks. Future challenges include planning for human resource for public health at State/national level, framing of State specific human resource development and training policy, creation of human resource management information system, reorientation of medical and para-medical education and ensuring proper utilization of the trained manpower and standardization of training. It is also important to link human resource development and training policy to the National Rural Health Mission in achieving its goals.

EVOLVING TERMS OF HUMAN RESOURCE MANAGEMENT AND DEVELOPMENT by **A. Haslinda** ^[11]: According to this article the term HRM and HRD were used by scholars, academics and practitioners. However, confusion arises on the terms or labels for HRM and HRD and its position in a management function. The purpose of this paper is to examine the evolving terms in human resource management (HRM) and human resource development (HRD). Based on a review of the literature, this paper draws the concepts surrounding the terms in human resource management and development. The findings highlight that the terms HRM and HRD have evolved along with globalization and rapid technological advances. Due to these changes in the environment, new terms are seen to be necessary to describe new ideas, concepts and philosophies of HRM and HRD. Currently, and in the near future, new terms will emerge to describe the philosophy of HRM and HRD. This paper suggests a need for practitioners to understand the various terms describing HRM and HRD before it is used in organizations rather than to use new terms to describe old ideas or functions of HRM and

HRD.

HUMAN RESOURCE MANAGEMENT- Issues and Challenges by **Dileep V. Mavalankar** ^[12]: This paper reviews the status of human resource systems in primary health care before the ICPD, the problems faced, the policy changes in the family planning program following ICPD and efforts made to reorient staff to the policy and programmatic changes. As the process has just begun in India, there is a long way to go. Therefore, the paper also discusses key challenges for the future in this monumental effort to reorient the Indian family planning program.

Managing Human Resources for Health in India- A case study of Gujarat & Madhya Pradesh by **Central Bureau of Health Intelligence, Dte. GHS, MOHFW, GOI In collaboration with World Health Organization - India Country Office** ^[13]: The study was conducted in two states – Madhya Pradesh & Gujarat. Madhya Pradesh was selected as a poor performing state and Gujarat as a better performing state based on health human resource indicators. The approach was to study the government records – rules, regulations and policies regarding management of health manpower in the states. The implementation mechanism and actual practices of human resource management was studied through interviews and discussion with the entire spectrum of officials and functionaries at state, district and field levels. In each of the state two districts were visited – One with better and the other having poor manpower available.

BUILDING CAPACITY IN HUMAN RESOURCES MANAGEMENT FOR HEALTH SECTOR REFORM AND THE ORGANIZATIONS AND INSTITUTIONS COMPRISING THE SECTOR by **Sarah Johnson** ^[14]: This article said about the importance of human resources management for the health sector reforms. It also prescribed tools for assessment of HRD.

HR AND NEW APPROACHES TO PUBLIC SECTOR MANAGEMENT: IMPROVING HRM CAPACITY by **Dr Stephen Bach** ^[15]: This article examined why building HR capacity is important to health care reforms and assesses the existing evidence of HR capability in the health sector and draw out lessons from existing practice.

PUBLIC HEALTH WORKFORCE IN INDIA: CAREER PATHWAYS FOR PUBLIC HEALTH PERSONNEL by **K. K. Datta** ^[16]: This document was prepared as a background paper for the National Consultation on Public Health Workforce in India, organized by the Ministry of Health & Family Welfare, Govt. Of India in collaboration with the WHO Country Office for India on 24-25, June 2009 at New Delhi.

Health Worker Shortages and Inequalities: The Reform of United States Policy by **Paula O'Brien and Lawrence O. Gostin** ^[17]: this paper said that the United States and other rich countries have done very little to address the dire global shortage of health workers. In some instances, the conduct of the world's richest countries has exacerbated the shortages experienced in poor countries. We advocate that the Obama Administration adopt two principal strategies to assist with solving the global health workforce crisis. The first strategy requires that a significant part of the U.S.'s development assistance for health be shifted towards building health systems in partner countries, in particular training and employing health workers to deal holistically

with the most pressing health problems experienced by the poor. Secondly, the U.S. should pursue a high level of national self-sufficiency in its health workforce and not continue its heavy reliance on recruitment of migrant health workers to fulfill the demand for health workers in the U.S.

Human Resources for Health in India's National Rural Health Mission: Dimension and Challenges by S K Satpathy and S Venkatesh ^[18]: This paper said that the task of ensuring the availability of MBBS doctors and specialists and to build capacity for rural health care in India is huge, but doable. The challenges include shortages, imbalances and low productivity, compounded by insufficient investment, inadequate pre-service training, migration, work overload, freeze in salaries and work environment issues (infrastructure, technical safety and community support). The overall shortages are aggravated by skewed distribution within the country, and even within the states, and movement of health personnel from rural to urban areas, from public sector to the private sector, or to jobs outside the health sector or overseas. The gaps within the existing infrastructure and the services both within and outside the public sector need to be addressed. However, just having the requisite numbers of health personnel is not enough.

India's Public Health System- How Well Does It Function at the National Level? By Monica Das Gupta and Manju Rani ^[19]: This article said that India has relatively poor health outcomes, despite having a well-developed administrative system, good technical skills in many fields, and an extensive network of public health institutions for research, training, and diagnostics. This suggests that the health system may be misdirecting its efforts, or be poorly designed. To explore this, we use instruments developed to assess the performance of public health systems in the United States and Latin America based on the framework of the Essential Public Health Functions identified as the basic functions that an effective public health system must fulfill. This paper focuses on the federal level in India, using data obtained from senior health officials in the central government. The data indicated that the reported strengths of the system lay in having the capacity to carry out most of the public health functions. Its reported weaknesses lie in three broad areas. First, it has overlooked some fundamental public health functions such as public health regulations and their enforcement. Second, deep management flaws hinder effective use of resources, including an inadequate focus on evaluation; on assessing quality of services; on dissemination and use of information; and an openness to learning and innovation. Resources could also be much better utilized with small changes, such as the use of incentives and challenge funds, and greater flexibility to reassign resources as priorities and needs change. Third, the central government functions too much in isolation and needs to work much more closely with other key actors, especially with sub-national governments, as well as with the private sector and with communities. We conclude that with some re-assessment of priorities and better management practices, health outcomes could be substantially improved.

Strategic Dynamics of the Project Based Organization by Stamboulis Yeoryios, Kalaouzis George ^[20]: This paper said that Project management is one of the most important and de-

manding fields of management. Cost and time overrides are more than common, while more organizations are becoming project-based. Through a systems perspective we develop a holistic view of the project based organization as a structure of resources committed to activities and the strategic decisions that involved in the operation of the organization. A system dynamics model is developed in the fashion of a balanced scorecard.

Creating Project-Based Organizations to Deliver Value by Michel Thiry ^[21]: Project-Based Organizations (PBO) are fast emerging as a serious trend, but many organizations still do not understand how to structure themselves to effectively create a strategic advantage from projects. PBOs need to be structured to create synergy between strategy, project, program and portfolio management and the project approach needs to both generate tangible value for the stakeholders and be sustainable. PBOs refer to a variety of organizational forms that involve the creation of temporary systems for the performance of project tasks or activities. They include matrix organizations, projected organizations and other forms of organizations that privilege a project approach for conducting their activities. PBOs are receiving increased consideration as an emerging organizational form, but many researchers report that there is very little knowledge on how project-based organizations actually operate in practice. There are also very few references on how extensive the use of unique and temporary endeavors like projects and programs can influence the strategy and the design of organizations. As the application of project management is spreading in organizations, one needs to understand the different project-based organizational models that can accommodate various situations and address the issues of compartmentalization, typical of traditionally structured organizations, versus integration, typical of networked organizations, as they structure their project-based organizations (PBOs).

The success of NRHM in India could be attributed partly to how effectively it introduced and practiced an HR policy (Kumar 2009). The significant deviations from the established norms of government rules were evident under the NRHM because a Government Department adopted methods of working like a projectified organization ^[22].

Several studies had made observations and suggestions that relate to the challenges for HRM in Project based organizations (PBOs). Many studies had said that innovative HR was possible with ease in PBOs in comparison with any traditional set ups and thus the performance of PBOs was quite remarkable ^[23]. It was reported by Thomas Miller that in order to promote performance more and more engineering and auto companies in Europe had turned itself into a project based organization ^[24].

4. Methods and materials:

Under the research an employee survey of over 600 employees was conducted. In addition, case studies of 52 cases were accomplished in six states of the country. Cases were taken in different states of the country. All kinds of health facilities such as Health Sub Centers (HSCs), Primary Health Centre (PHCs), Community Health Centers (CHCs), First Referral Units (FRUs) and District Hospitals (DHs) were taken as cases. Similarly varied kind of people such as Accredited Social Health Activists (ASHAs), An-

ganwadi workers (AWWs), Auxiliary Nurse and Midwives (ANMs), Medical Officers, Management Professionals, High ranked government bureaucrats, Peoples representatives, Non-governmental organizations and common citizens were interviewed with the help of structured and semi structured questionnaire. The survey was conducted by email and also by written questionnaire, meeting people face to face and recording the responses. E-mail address of high ranked bureaucrats and management professional engaged under NRHM were availed from visiting various websites of the State health societies and national portal www.mohfw.nic.in. A letter of invitation to participate in the survey along with a questionnaire was sent to them. In certain cases, repeated requests were sent by e-mail. In turn almost 45 such bureaucrats and management professional from throughout the country responded out which 36 responses were usable and used under the research. Points were allocated for each question. In case of ratings such as strongly agree, agree, disagree or strongly disagree point such as 5, 4, 1 and 0 were allocated respectively. The observation presented in this paper was based on such ratings and points.

The criteria for evaluation and assessment through the HR tool included computerization of data, personnel files, job classification system, compensation and benefits, 3 R's i.e. Recruitment, Retention, and Retirement; Talent & Knowledge Management; Onboarding and Orientation; Policy and Planning; Laws Compliance; Leadership development; and Discipline, termination and grievance procedures.

The human resource capacity of the NRHM was assessed under this research as State health societies of six states, Bihar, Jharkhand, Chhattisgarh, Madhya Pradesh, Uttar Pradesh and Uttaranchal were examined under the process. The assessment also covered 23 district health societies which included five district health societies in each state as mentioned earlier.

The HCM functions assessed by the case study fall into the category of personnel administration, including HR policies, hiring processes and employee contracts, personnel files, performance appraisal, conflict resolution, and assuring compliance with labor laws. They were also involved in the payroll and staffing contingency plans.

HRM was generally not responsible for staff training in any of these societies as training schedule under NHM was observed by other functionaries at several levels which was most unique. In all cases the HRM or HR Management unit was within the purviews of respective state health societies. Tasks were carried out by personnel assigned to this area. The human resource management functions were carried out at the central level in all of the organizations, except one where they had decentralized some of the functions. Some of the HRM challenges faced by the state health societies were in the form of training staff for new roles and assuring integrated, functioning teams. It was required to assess HR management in following sequence:-

HR Capacity: It was critical that this component addressed first. If the assessment of HR capacity (budget and staff) was at a level 4 or 2, meaning there were enough budget available, but no qualified staff charged with HR responsibility, the institution or organization could not address the other HR components.

HR Planning: Next in order of importance was HR Planning. The organizational mission provided direction to the HR strategies and the HR Plan provided direction to the work that people do.

HR Policy: All of the elements included under HR policy provided an essential framework for defining the terms and conditions of work and need to be in place before effective performance management and supervisory systems could be implemented.

HR Data: In addition to the above components, organizations required some means of tracking the people who worked for them. They also needed employee data to accurately project employment needs. This component was addressed in a timely fashion

Performance: Performance management and supervisory systems defined how people would interact with each other and how the work that they did.

Management: It would support the goals of the institution or organization.

Training: Training was an essential component of an effective HR System, but it was most effective when it was managed and integrated into the other components of HR planning, policy and performance management.

Organizations were also asked specific questions about: the role of HCM in their organization, current HCM challenges they faced, involvement of their organization in health sector reform; and any new HRM challenges arising from this involvement. The e-mail address of national level, several state level and district level functionaries under NRHM were searched with the help of Google search on the internet and picked. The HR assessment tool and questions were also emailed to 15 State health societies (SHSs) and the central NRHM mission directorate with a cover letter and a set of instructions. Six SHSs responded. The instrument was applied in these 6 organizations, according to the specifications on the assessment process described above. They were asked to return the consensus assessment scores to scholar, with 1-2 indicators that provided supporting evidence for the scores they assigned, in addition to responses to the questions mentioned above.

The scores on assessment tool applied to 6 State Health Societies are displayed in tabular form as **Table-1**. Therefore, please see in **Table-1**. The numbers on the top of the HR assessment tool matrix refer to the stages of development. Stage 1 is, the less developed stage; stage 4 is the most developmental stages. It is not uncommon at any given time for organizations to be in different stages of development of the HCM different components of the HR instrument. The human resource management characteristics refer to the statements that describe the HR component at each stage of development. The indicators are the measures or observations that offer evidence of a general status or condition.

The components described in this instrument relate to the different parts of an HR system. Some of these descriptor structure and organizational elements, e.g., Staffing, Budget. Other components describe policy requirements. Some of the components described management systems that were critical to managing HR, e.g, Performance Management, Supervision. Some of the

components relate to staff training and development activities. An effective HR management system integrates all of these components.

5. Results:

The general trend in the government sector of transferring themselves in PBOs could be described as consisting of two principal patterns of change in relation to the structuring of firms; (1) that the new set up increasingly start off as PBOs and (2) that traditional functional organizations change into relying more on PBOs. In the case of NRHM both principles were applied.

PBOs carry out most of its core activities in projects and there were numerous public health programs in the public health sector of India. This means that the project form was considered to be the most effective one for its operations. Most studies that discussed the reasons for organizing by projects highlighted the 'knowledge economy' and the need to integrate knowledge resources in a fast and flexible way in order to reach a defined goal in a certain time [23].

The use of PBOs of carrying out the core operations also means that much work was being carried out in cross-functional teams. Projects integrated competencies across functional lines – they comprise members that represent different specialties and different competence bases. The choice of project-based work systems, hence implied a focus on cross-functional work in projects instead of functional departments for carrying out core activities. A PBO should consequently be characterized by cross-functional [24]. The public health sector also crosses functioned in multiple dimensions. In PBOs, project work was routine rather than the exception, which implied that people perform most of their work in time-limited temporary projects [23]. Most of the programs in the public health sector were limited by a distinct time, however, their tenure mostly getting extended as a routine.

PBOs could be a time bound framework in which temporary projects were embedded. But such temporary arrangements could be part of a permanent structure. Such temporary embeds in any permanent structure could create tensions among temporary and permanent systems. Such issues were quite a phenomenon and reported existing under NRHM and also under other programs of "Education for All" in India. Therefore, PBOs were characterized by an inherent tension between permanent and temporary systems [25].

In a PBO, people were employed by the organization and not by individual projects. This implied that the relation between employees and the organization generally goes beyond the time scope of an individual project. However, in this context, being 'employed' does not necessarily equal having a permanent employment contract in the PBOs. Therefore, the workforce that contributed to the organization's activities consists of 'permanent' employees, but also of a significant number of more 'temporary' employees such as consultants, self-employed professionals and others with temporary contracts. In other words, the PBOs were often characterized by heterogeneity in employment relations.

The survey revealed that MOHFW opting for PBO approach was mainly due to financial constraints. 86.14% said that government

was not having adequate funds to fund the social sector adequately. Similarly, 88.92% said that it would be easy to remove staffs engaged in contractual basis than permanent basis. Almost 92.43% said that they were not certain about the fate of employees after the tenure of NRHM being ended in April 2012.

44.34% complained about place of posting and work conditions. Almost 66.76% were not satisfied with their present salary. 73.98% wanted permanent quarters if posted in remote areas. 56.12% said that they were not satisfied with the doctors engaging in private practices as it hurts the public health system. Almost 49.37% said that there were no performance based incentives. 66.62% said that they lack career growth opportunities under NRHM.

Findings of the case study:

Case studies and HR assessment tool showed that there was lack of HR professionals under NRHM at various levels. It was true that some HR professionals were available at the state level, but at the district and sub district level, there were no HR professionals and HR functions were discharged by other persons not experienced to perform HR actions. Further the case study showed that in several states, especially in Bihar and Jharkhand there was the absentee system whereby absentee was required to be submitted by the employees through competent authorities on a monthly basis on the basis of which salary was paid. There was a situation whereby a District Program Manager in Jharkhand was not paid a salary for the one and half year as he was posted simultaneously in three districts and asked to submit absentee after approval of civil surgeons of all three districts which not became possible and salary was not paid. Finally the person resigned. Case study also showed that in several states there was not adequate work conditions and supply of logistics, supportive staff were not accomplished within the prescribed time limit. Case study also found that private practice by government doctors were allowed in several states. The case studies revealed that most of the employees used persuasion to senior and competent authorities to remain posted in urban areas or any nearby area in close proximity to urban centers.

HR actions under NRHM:

A. Establishing the requirement of manpower: One of the major HR actions under NRHM had been to increase the total number of posts by firming up norms under Indian Public Health Standards. This process was known as identification of a gap in manpower which was a part of the overall gap analysis conducted in the form of facility surveys under NRHM.

B. Recruitment: The recruitment process under NRHM was also most unique because it both centralized and diversified on the same pattern of overall HR Management. A sizeable amount of the recruitments was done by the state level society, whereas district health societies were also involved in the recruitment of some key personnel such as staff for Program Management Units, Hospital managers, Lab technicians, Health supervisors etc.

Usually advertisements were published in different newspapers and also posted on various websites of the State level and district level societies seeking job applications from eligible candidates. Services of recruiting agencies such as SAMS and FEED BACK

VENTURES were also availed in some cases. Hiring of recruitment agencies such as SAMS, FEEDBACK VENTURES and others was done for recruitment of the key positions in a situation where specialized qualifications were required. Services of recruiting agencies were mostly availed by central agencies and in some cases, state health societies also ensured their services. In such cases advertisement was published in newspapers and candidates were asked to submit online applications or submit resumes by e-mail.

It was found that fixed salary was offered without any provisions of the HRA, PF/GPF etc. Throughout the country the recruitments were done on almost similar pattern with some differences in salary offered, experiences and qualifications desirable. At several places applications were also accepted online. Especially SAMS accepted applications online. The varied kind of stuff was recruited under various programs of NRHM. The approach of recruitments did vary from level to level and from state to state. Written tests, computer ability tests and interviews were organized in order to shortlist candidates before final selection. List of successful candidates was provided to authorities by private agencies which in turn invited candidates to join as soon as possible.

C. Training: Training under the NRHM was one of the most challenging HR functions. The nature, kind and diversity of the training required under the NRHM was so extensive that it was an uphill task in enabling adequate training for all kinds of stuff. A health care delivery system under NRHM was prone to change with advancement in technology or methods. It was required to keep pace with the advancement in medical technology. Creation of infrastructure, supply of logistics and training on new methods was required repeatedly under NRHM.

The major focus of NRHM was to provide all primitive, preventive and curative services needed by the people in an integrated approach, so that services were provided through a single window. In order to achieve this, it was imperative that Health, Family Welfare and AYUSH programs were effectively integrated and delivered through an effectively functioning primary health care infrastructure.

MOHFW was enabled to bring out a concise document outlining training strategy for service providers at district and below. This document was useful for state and central officials and policy makers understand the training for effective integrated Health, Family Welfare and AYUSH service delivery at sub district levels [26].

D. Multi-Skilling: Improving workforce skills required a systematic program of in service training. Current training programs were almost completely linked to the national health programs and even within these divided into IMNCI, SBA, adolescent and reproductive health, training in IUD insertion, training for different types of sterilization surgery and for safe abortion etc., each of which was proceeding independently of the other. There was no way of even measuring how many facilities now had all these skills in place and were using it and the training institutions were not charged with ensuring that each facility had the requisite skills in place. Therefore, efforts were to build up district and regional training centers and state institutes of health and family welfare, but they were limited to transmitting, as unchanged as

possible these above packages to a fixed number of persons every year with little certainty of what becomes of it after they have left the training hall. Beyond these fixed RCH and RNTCP type training packages other dimension of the IPHS specified service package was being addressed.

Multi-Skilling was one major option for getting the skill mix required within the available human resource of the department. There were three areas where such multi-Skilling was encouraged under the NRHM.

a. Multi Skilling of technicians and paramedics: Paramedical especially laboratory technicians posted in remote areas were trained for curative clinical skills and first aid skills. But this training was not uniformly implemented in all states. Tripura and Chhattisgarh had taken the lead in a direction.

a. Multi-Skilling of nurses: The specific proposal in this regard had been for the creation of nurse practitioners, in a context where there were no women doctors and often no doctors at all. Some functions like RTI (Reproductive tract infections) management needed women doctors and indeed in all functions this was welcome. Counseling, adolescent clinics, regular follow up on non-communicable disease, were other functions that nurses could perform.

c. Multi-Skilling of medical officers for specialist's tasks: Multi-Skilling for specialist skills needed for emergency obstetric care was the area where the most visible advance had been made. The systems for this had been put in place and the legal challenges had been engaged with. One aspect worth noting was that in many states a fair number of medical officers were providing surgical and anesthetist skills and they were under pressures to stop doing so. However, given the fact that as recently as 20 years back this has been the main form of surgical skill availability in the public health system, it would make more sense to prioritize such officers for certification through short term courses so that the startup times reduced.

E. Use of modern tool and techniques: NRHM witnessed a significant impact on the broad approach of various HR actions. Recruitments tests were conducted online with the use of sophisticated desktops and laptops. New technologies were broadly used, particularly in the areas of electronic communication and information dissemination and retrieval, had dramatically altered the landscape. Satellite communications, computers and networking systems, fax machines, and other devices had all facilitated change in the ways in which employees interacted with each other and their headquarters. Telecommuting, for instance, had become a very popular option for many employees, and HRM professionals had to develop new guidelines for this emerging subset of employees.

Impacts of HRM under NRHM

The HR management under NRHM was unique which had created some tangible impact on the public health system of the country. At least two areas were more significant and they were:-

a. Outsourcing and Public Private Partnerships (PPP): Various initiatives had been employed in an attempt to increase efficiency in the public health system. For example, outsourcing of services had been used to convert fixed labor expenditures into variable

costs as a means of improving efficiency. Contracting-out, performance contracts and internal contracting were also examples of measures employed largely under the NRHM. Under PPP at various places diagnostics and institutional services were outsourced.

b. Gender equity and fairness: NRHM never discriminated against women, thus key personnel such as ANMs, AWWs and ASHAs all being women. It was evident that there was numerically adequate for women under NRHM. This was perhaps one of the feats of HR practices. Besides, it could be also seen that in each PHC there would be a lady doctor at least. Therefore, it could be seen that NRHM was one of the program where gender bias never existed in theory at least. At the mental level, gender bias may exist which were more individual in nature. The largest number of women were employed in capacity of managers and administrative set up and most of them found to be doing extremely well.

Many human resources initiatives under NRHM also included attempts to increase equity or fairness. Strategies aimed at promoting equity in relation to needs required more systematic planning of health services. Some of these strategies included the introduction of financial protection mechanisms, the targeting of specific needs and groups, and re-deployment services. One of the goals of human resource professionals under NRHM was to use these and other measures to increase equity.

HR constraints under NRHM

One of the greatest constraints before the HRM under the NRHM was due to two sets of the workforce engaged. One was expected to be governed by the respective state government rules while for other NRHM rules applied. It would be noted that all health employees could not said to be employed under NRHM despite they were providing services under NRHM.

a. The size of work force: The size of the workforce engaged under NRHM was quite high. It almost approximated to be around 2.5 million in the whole country. The managing every affair of HR actions was quite challenging for all those employees. The performance appraisal was quite challenging because in certain cases, especially for ASHAs performance based incentives were provisioned.

b. Workforce Training: Workforce training was another most challenging issue. It was essential that human resources personnel consider the composition of the health workforce in terms of both skill categories and training levels. New options for the education and in-service training of health care workers were required to ensure that the workforce was aware of and prepared to meet a particular state's present and future needs. A properly trained and competent workforce was essential to any successful health care system.

b. The private practice of medical officers: Private practice by government doctors and paramedics, technicians were more common in some states. It was so prevalent in Bihar and Jharkhand that almost doctors were having their clinics and nursing homes, pathological centres.

The issue of government specialists doing private practice was another major issue that was raised. Andhra reported, in particu-

lar, quoting a case from Nalgonda states that this "has become a vested interest in the public health provider, not to operationalise emergency obstetric care. To make the matter worse the ANMs and ASHAs under the MO in charge may become agents for taking the C-section cases to the private clinics being run by them and earn some extra bucks." This report had called for better monitoring of hiring specialists as an immediate measure of improving workforce performance.

d. Transfer and posting of doctors and paramedics: The issue of a lack of a transfer and posting policy impeding workforce management and workforce morale had been reported from many states.

Transfer procedure required to involve counseling and transparency wherein the list of vacancies was put in the public domain and doctors could put in their requests for their posting to the place of their choice with formidable logic and reasons.

e. The migration of work force: The migration of health care workers was an issue that became prominent when examining state's health care systems. Research outlined that the movement of health care professionals closely followed the migration pattern of all professionals in that the internal movement of the workforce in urban areas was common to all states. It was noticed that there was utmost willingness to get stationed in some urban areas where better power, transport and other amenities were available. A lot of persuasion was practiced regarding persuasion of authorities to get posted at desired locations. Such unwanted workforce mobility created additional imbalances that required better workforce planning, attention to issues of pay and other rewards and improved overall management of the workforce.

f. Incremental measures missing: In addition to salary incentives, it was required to use other strategies such as housing, infrastructure and opportunities for job rotation to recruit and retain health professionals, since many health workers were underpaid, poorly motivated and very dissatisfied. The migration and the motivation of health workers were an important human resources issue that required being carefully measured and monitoring.

g. State's level of income: Another issue that arose when examining HRM under NRHM was a state's level of economic development. There was evidence of a significant positive correlation between the level of economic development in a state and its number of human resources for health. States with a higher gross domestic product (GDP) and per capita spend more on health care than states with lower GDP and they tended to have larger health workforces.

h. Cultural and geographical: It was also found essential that cultural and geographical factors be considered when implementing HR policy under NRHM. Geographical factors such as climate or topography used to influence the ability to deliver health services; the cultural and political values of a particular state could also affect the demand and supply of human resources for health.

i. Two types of employees: The new arrangements under NRHM resulted in two types of employees in one set up. One was permanent government employees while another was contractual

staff. The salary to the permanent staff was paid by state governments through their treasuries, but contractual staff was paid through society route.

HRM challenges under NRHM:

It could be outlined that there were following challenges in HRM practices under NRHM:-

i. Competence-related challenges:

- a. Achieving long-term competence development.
- b. Finding adequate career structures.
- c. Retaining knowledge while people move across organizational boundaries.

ii. Performance-related challenges:

- a. Designing trustworthy and effective performance reviews.
- b. Facilitating 'swift trust' and defending project's workers' reputation.

iii. Individual-related challenges:

- a. Managing the requirements placed upon on 'professional project workers'.
- b. Managing high work intensity.

Most of the HR activities under NRHM were performed by non HR professional. Services of qualified HR professionals were not available at district and sub district level. Even at the state level just one or two HR professionals were available.

It was also evident that there were no opportunities for retention of the work force. Several new recruits deserted the job in short span of time. The lack of career growth opportunities and unrewarding job were the main reasons, but in some cases the lethargic and biased approaches by permanent employees also said to be a reason for new professionals quitting the job earlier than expected. A public health sector of the country always depended upon qualitative and skilled workforce therefore quick changeover by professionals could severely harm the prospects. Thus the more focus required for retention and career growth opportunities.

The key findings of HR assessment tool applied have been presented in **table-2**; therefore please see in **table 2**.

6. Discussion:

It was observed and opening by several persons that HCM consideration was one of the major factors which induced Ministry of health and family welfare (MOHFW), Government of India to opt for a TB-PBO approach to correct things in the public health sector. It might be true to an extent, but this research found nothing specific to validate this point. Government may have adopted such approach due to fund crunch, but there could be many other considerations also which were not taken up in this study.

But it was sure that TB-PBO approach provided ample opportunity to exercise innovative HCM policies which most suited to attain the objectives even under a governmental cover. Definitely it was not possible for any government structure to implement

useful HCM policies under the regime of existing governance principles and laws. Therefore, it could be said that government was seemingly quite logical to opt for a TB-PBO approach to attain their objectives in limited periods. And this approach was quite justified under those circumstances.

It was also evident that Ministry of health and family welfare, Government of India was finding it difficult due to certain restraints to address the key health issues and challenges of the country though the established style of functioning guided by strict rules and regulations. Also, there was no uniformity among states in the style of governance. Certain regulations required frequent modifications and rearrangements which was not possible under the existing government administration. Thus, they rightly entrepreneur to venture into a project based approach or mission oriented approach in order to attain their public health objectives in a short period of time. This venture could be reflected in the form of the National Rural Health Mission which in turn enabled the union government to exercise innovative ideas in quick succession of time. Some other government departments also adopted similar measures to achieve their long term social-developmental objectives within a limited period, the example could be 'Sarva Shikha Abhiyan' launched by the Ministry of education, Government of India. There were other examples also.

It was quite evident that the country's public health challenges were massive and they required large scale intervention. The capacity of the government was limited mainly due to funding shortages and lack of skilled persons in the government sector. Skilled workforce was required in a short period for shorter term. It was also necessary to retrench new employees the moment objectives were fulfilled. Thus a government set up ventured to create a project based organization with the view of adopting innovative HR policies for the maximum benefits involving low cost and within a prescribed time period.

No doubt several institutional arrangements were done at the state level to district level and further up to sub district levels. Some earlier version of institutions was merged into new institutions. Such institutions were mainly in the form of a registered society which was inclusive of members from both government and non-government sector. Such institutions, though received funds from the government, but legally could not be a said to be government entities. Such institutions accomplished recruitments for projects mainly on a contractual basis.

There were several literatures which had criticized NRHM for low salaries and employing people on a contractual basis. It was usual that a government set up usually appointed persons on a permanent basis for most of its work. But under NRHM the task was so vast and the number of required workforce was also huge therefore it was provisioned to perform recruitments on a contractual basis. This was done with the purpose that moment the work is over or objectives accomplished the employees would be sacked immediately without any further consideration. This was most prevalent in PBOs world over.

It was evident that under NRHM different health projects were implemented under different programs such as Reproductive and Child Health Program, Several disease control programs, family

welfare programs, etc. For each projects different kind of skilled work force was required at different levels for a short period. Thus, employees were appointed on contractual basis whereby a short term contract was offered to them ranging from one to five years. This was done with the view that they could to automatically stand removed from service the moment their contract was not further extended. Such practices were also not surprising these days commonly known as hire and fire policy.

It was also observed that the performance of contractual staff was more impressive than permanent staff. It was well evident from this fact that most of the permanent staff in the health department was already working with them since long, but the difference could be noticed only after recruitment and on job placement of the contractual staff under NRHM since 2005 onwards. Therefore, it could be said with full certainty that contractual staff had out performed permanent staff under NRHM. This could be indicative of a successful HRM policy under NRHM.

Private practice by government doctors, transfer and posting and job reservation were some gray areas in the HR field under NRHM. Job reservation policy is a political and complex issue, but other issues required to be tackled effectively. Volunteers would be beneficial in the development sector, but lot of volunteers seen in the name of ASHA. Country public health issues could not be handled in the name of such sheer volunteerism. Outsourcing and PPP were some areas which required attentiveness. Everything could not outsourced and run in PPP mode.

Another major issue required to be debated that how entire gamut of HR actions were performed by non HR professionals. It was found that doctors, paramedics and administrative staff were indulged largely in HR actions in which they were not having any experience of expertise. After all, how a public health sector who was having deficient medical, paramedical manpower could afford that their medical and paramedical staff devote much of their skill and time in managing other affairs such as logistics, HR management and other.

The country's public health sector was facing acute shortage of medical and paramedical personnel therefore multi Skilling of manpower has to be promoted. The salary and compensation discrepancies required to be eliminated in one go.

7. Conclusion:

HRM policy adopted under NRHM was seemingly highly compatible with the mandate of public health objectives in India in the short run, however, it has the potential to destroy the entire public health system as a part of the culture. Several basic HR management principles and theories have been critically ignored that would cost the public health system heavily. A project based approach aimed at achieving certain developmental goals in the short run would not be enough. There were strategic HR policy and it was expected to achieve public health objectives without those HR policies.

8. Tables:

Table 1: Scores of HR assessment tool applied to 6 state health societies.

HR component	SHS, Jharkhand	SHS, UP	SHS Chhattisgarh	SHS, Bihar	SHS, Ut-taranchal	SHS, MP
HR budget	3	4	4	2	4	2

HR staff	2	3	4	3	4	3
Mission and goals of the organization	4	2	4	3	3	3
HR planning	3	1	3	2	4	2
Job classification system	1	2	3	3	4	3
Compensation and benefits	4	2	2	2	3	2
Recruitment and hiring	3	2	4	4	3	4
Employee orientation program	3	1	3	1	4	1
Policy manuals	3	2	4	4	4	4
Discipline, termination, grievances	3	1	4	2	3	2
Relationship with unions	4	3	4	4	4	4
Labor law compliance	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
Employee Data	3	2	3	3	4	3
Computerization of data	4	2	4	4	4	4
Personnel files	4	2	4	3	4	3
Job descriptions	4	2	3	2	4	2
Supervision	3	2	3	2	4	2
Planning and performance review	4	2	2	1	4	1
Training	4	1	4	3	4	3
Management and leadership training	3	2	3	2	3	2
Links to external pre – service Institutions	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA

Table 7: Key findings of HRM assessment tools

HR component	Findings
HR budget	Sufficient budget to operate a well-structured HR department could be available or proposed through PIPs but it appeared that at most places the HR unit was not adequately developed which showed the lack of importance provided to HRM. HRM was required for development of public health sector and health sector reform
HR staff	It was found that each health society examined was not having adequate HR persons though 1-2 HR managers were definitely available but they were not adequate to effectively handle the entire gamut of HR actions required for such a huge manpower.
Mission and goals of the organization	Missions and goals were well articulated.
HR planning	There was no specialized HR planning system at any level could be visible.
Job classification system	Current job descriptions were on file. Procedure to maintain and implement them required sustainability.
Compensation & Benefits	Compensation and benefits available as per rule.
Recruitment and hiring	Recruitment and hiring was a continuous process. People were coming in and also going out. Retention was not adequate. It required developing a formidable health system.
Employee Orientation Program	Several orientation programs organized for core staff such as doctors, paramedics and technicians as per the national training

	schedule.
Policy manuals	There was no any HR policy manual developed or could be visible at any place.
Discipline, termination, Grievance	Disciplinary actions and terminations were practiced. The grievance redressal system required development.
Relationship with unions	The relationships with different employee unions were not so smooth and continuous.
Labor law compliance	Compliance with any labour laws was not evident.
Employee Data	Employee data was not adequately maintained and regulated.
Computerization of data	Computerization of data was not done at most places.
Personnel files	Personnel files not adequately maintained.
Job descriptions	Job descriptions were articulated but not properly monitored and supervised.
Supervision	Supervision was done at several levels for several staff.
Planning and performance review	Performance was not adequately reviewed.
Training	A dedicated training manual was developed for varied kind of staff.
Management and leadership training	It was not implemented universally and routinely.
Links to external pre-service institutions	Not evident.

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